

ETHNOLINGUISTIC AND ETHNOTOPONYMIC UNITS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP

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Abstract: This article describes the definition of the term ethnolinguistic units and ethnotoponymic units and the appearance of ethnotoponyms in ethnic forms. Among them, the ethnotoponyms of the world and Karakalpakstan are also listed.

Key words: Ethnolinguistics, ethnotoponomics, ethnoculture, areal linguistics, ethnonym.

Ethnolinguistics (ethno... and linguistics) is a field of linguistics that studies the relationship and relationship between language and the people who own the language, the combined influence of linguistic and ethnic factors on the functional characteristics of language development. The interaction between language and ethnic characteristics, the influence on each other is twofold: the influence of ethnic factors (ethnos' customs, national traditions, philosophical, religious views, etc.) on language development and, on the contrary, the positive influence of language functional capabilities on the formation of ethnos and ethnic characteristics. Ethnolinguistics studies how different ethnic groups have contributed to the language and its development, the features of closeness, commonality or their separation and distance between ethnic groups in this process. Ethnic onomastics, areal linguistics, linguistic geography, dialectology, language history, sociolinguistics, cartography are the fields of linguistics. Ethnolinguistics uses the achieved scientific results. Ethnolinguistics is especially useful in the study of the ethnography of peoples who do not have writing, in the collection and research of linguistic materials related to the ethnic characteristics of their languages.

Ethnolinguistics is a branch of the anthropocentric paradigm that studies the interaction of people's language and culture with each other. Ethnolinguistics aims to study people's life through their language.

Ethnolinguistics studies how different ethnic groups have contributed to the language and its development, the features of closeness, commonality or their separation and distance between ethnic groups in this process. Ethnic onomastics, areal linguistics, linguistic geography, dialectology, language

history, sociolinguistics, cartography use scientific results of ethnolinguistics. Ethnolinguistics is especially useful in the study of the ethnography of peoples who do not have writing, in the collection and research of linguistic materials related to the ethnic characteristics of their languages.

It is known that ethnolinguistics is a branch of linguistics that studies the relationship between a people (nation, people) and its language on the basis of ethnolinguistics (the principle of ethnic culture and ethnic language commonality).

It mainly works in two directions:

- study the ethnolinguistic character of the people on a descriptive basis;
- to study the ethno-linguistic character of the people on a recommendation basis.

The first goal can be conditionally called an external goal, and the second an internal goal. The relationship between language and ethnic characteristics, their influence on each other is a two-way process:

- the influence of the ethnic factor (custom, tradition, philosophical, religious views, etc.) on language development;
- the influence of the linguistic factor on the development of ethnos (and ethnic characteristics).

Let's say that ethnic features (customs, traditions, philosophical, religious views) are forgotten in a nation, and correspondingly, the linguistic units that represent them also leave the active linguistic treasure and become a reality of the past. As a result, the identity of the nation, people, and people begins to be damaged. The nation, the people, the people are losing their spirituality. This is inevitably reflected in the active lexicon. In the lexicon of the language, the ethnographic microsystem begins to decline. This is the influence of ethnic factors on the language. Ultimately, the ethnolinguistic gap in the minds of the children of the nation, which does not have an ethnographic lexicon, is filled with extraneous linguistic elements. Separation of the influence of language and ethnic characteristics is only for research purposes, this separation is relative in nature, in fact it is a continuous and organic process in which they occur as a whole.

Ethnolinguistics studies the contribution of ethnic groups to the language and its development, as well as the characteristics of closeness, commonality or separation and distance between ethnic groups in this process. This is more important for the first, external goal mentioned above. For the first purpose, work is done on the basis of a more descriptive research methodology.

The fields of linguistics, ethnic nomenclature (onomastics), areal (territorial) linguistics, linguistic geography, dialectology (linguistics), language history, sociolinguistics, cartography, use the scientific results obtained by this descriptive method of ethnolinguistics.

Ethnolinguistics, especially in the study of the ethnography of peoples who do not have writing, and in the collection and research of linguistic materials related to the ethnic character of their languages, manifests its first purpose more. The study of ethnographisms is directly related to the sciences of historical ethnology. If ethnology studies customs, people's way of life and the historical processes connected with them, the lexicon of customs and traditions (ethnographic lexicon) is the object of study of linguistics. It is impossible to imagine the culture of any nation without its customs, traditions and values. The study of ethnographies united under the name of ethnographic lexicon is important in the study of national customs and values. Traditions show the peculiarities of a certain ethnos, have an active place as a linguistic sign in the entire ethnographic system, and are therefore important for linguistics. In the lexical macrosystem of each language, there is a system of lexemes representing an ethnographic concept, which forms a separate microsystem. A special field of linguistics - ethnolinguistics - was formed to study these lexemes, which, as a linguistic field, studies both linguistic universals and specific aspects. Therefore, general and specific ethnolinguistics are distinguished. While general ethnolinguistics deals with general issues such as the emergence and development of ethnographic language phenomena, specific ethnolinguistics studies ethnographies specific to certain languages from this point of view.

In the following years, ethnolinguistic studies became active in the field of linguistics. Aspects of interdependence of language and culture are revived in world linguistics as an example of ethnolinguistics in the genres of folk mentality, spiritual culture, folk oral creativity, mythology, folklore. Ethnolinguistics emerged as an independent field of science in the 19th and 20th centuries and developed in the USA in the 1970s. D. H. Hames, H. Hoyer, G. M. Hoengiswald, and the study of the problem in Russia of the influence of socio-cultural factors on language in world linguistics is associated with the names of F. I. Buslaev, A. N. Afanasyev, A. A. Potebnya.

In linguistics, for ethnographic analysis, in most cases, concept names related to folk customs and traditions are taken as objects. The study of ethnographies in Karakalpak linguistics was started mainly in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century. The scientific researches of M. I. Byatushgova, A. K. Apoyev,

etc. also made a great contribution to the study of ethnographies in Turkish linguistics.

Toponymy is of scientific and practical importance with a number of scientific fields. By studying toponyms, it is possible to determine many historical facts, the territorial boundaries of some peoples and clans, program, tradition, culture, and language differences, as well as various features of a specific terrain, flora and fauna, with the help of toponymics.

Only the language can capture and preserve information about ethnos with a complete source and pass it on to the generations. According to this feature, we can say that the phenomenon of language is the basis of knowing the ethnos itself. It seems that all features of the language are completely included in this concept: language is the basis for the emergence of ethnos, the core of spiritual-cultural life, and the dimension of self-knowledge.

The emergence, formation and development of ethnotoponymy is a long and complex historical process, which is connected with various social, historical and linguistic factors. Geographical names representing the ethnic composition of the population, which clan, tribe, nation they belong to constitute a large group among any territorial toponymy.

In conclusion, ethnotoponyms were created on the basis of ethnonyms. One of the main areas of toponymy is the ethnotoponymy, which can be used to determine the areas inhabited by ancient peoples. We cannot study ethnotoponymy without thoroughly studying ethnonyms.

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